

GenderSAFE
ENDING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN ACADEMIA

A Safer European Research Area

Report on National Policies to Counteract Gender-Based Violence

Key Findings

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OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE

This report supports European Research Area coordination on counteracting gender-based violence in research and innovation and higher education by (i) mapping national policy instruments addressing gender-based violence; (ii) analysing the comprehensiveness of national policy frameworks and their alignment with the 2024 Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct across the three pillars (Commitment, Action, Accountability); (iii) identifying gaps and areas where policy design remains underdeveloped or insufficiently operationalised; (iv) documenting recent and ongoing policy developments; and (v) informing future EU-level coordination by highlighting policy needs and opportunities for further alignment. The intended coverage was EU-27 and Associated Countries engaged in ERA governance; 18 countries submitted complete responses in this reporting cycle.

METHODOLOGY IN BRIEF

Data were collected via the GenderSAFE Task 5.4 questionnaire administered through LimeSurvey between 13 October and 16 December 2025, supported by guidance, reminders and bilateral follow-up. To assess policy comprehensiveness, indicators were applied using predefined rules and thresholds across a five-category scale (Comprehensive, Developing, Intermediary, Emerging, Absent). For pillar-level analysis (Commitment/Action/Accountability), only countries with dedicated instruments addressing R&I and higher education were included (N=12).

MAIN FINDINGS

This section presents the main findings, pointing to a policy field that has been maturing rapidly in several national contexts, with evidence of progress since 2023 and increasing adoption of sector-specific instruments. Yet it also highlights structural issues: progress is more visible in terms of new instruments adopted and in the articulation of institutional actions required or recommended by the national policies from the obligated institutions, but in some cases without systemic, intersectional framing (Commitment) and, most critically, without enforceable monitoring, reporting and evaluation (Accountability).

POLICY TRAJECTORIES ARE EMERGING

Early starters are moving into policy review and reinforcement, while newer adopters are developing new sector-specific policies and initiatives.

The monitoring reveals distinct trajectories of national policy development. A first group of **early starters** (Ireland, France) has established dedicated sector-specific frameworks and is now moving toward review, renewal, and strengthening. Ireland is revising its 2019 national framework through an expert review and stakeholder consultation process, with implementation of a revised framework planned for 2026; France signals continuation of its 2021–2025 national action plan and preparation of a new roadmap following evaluation.

A second trajectory is visible among **newer adopters, including widening countries (Czechia, Denmark, Poland)**, where sector-specific provisions are becoming more visible through new standards, funded initiatives, and instruments, even if in some instances a dedicated policy framework may still be under development.

A third pattern is observed in countries with **long-standing gender mainstreaming governance frameworks** (Sweden, Iceland), where established gender equality requirements are in place but have not recently been complemented by new policy measures specifically targeting research and innovation and higher education. This suggests that while gender mainstreaming can provide an important framework, it does not ensure further sector-specific policy evolution.

A HETEROGENEOUS LANDSCAPE

Policy mixes are expanding, but dedicated instruments remain limited to a small group of countries.

Across the responding countries, the results confirm that national frameworks addressing gender-based violence in R&I and higher education are highly uneven in both scope and addressing specifically the higher education and/or research and innovation sectors. Only a small set of countries currently combine instruments dedicated to the R&I and higher education sector with a broader national policy or law in a way that produces an overall comprehensive policy mix.

- **Comprehensive** sets of instruments (dedicated policy/law in place): **Belgium, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal.**
- **Developing** sets of instruments (general policy/law AND a dedicated initiative): **Austria, Czechia, Denmark, Poland.**
- **Intermediary** sets of instruments (general policy/law OR dedicated initiatives): **Lithuania, Sweden, Norway.**
- **Emerging** sets of instruments (general national plans on gender-based violence /violence against women without explicitly addressing R&I and higher education): **Croatia, Slovakia, Albania, Iceland.**
- **Absent** sets of instruments (general law on gender equality and/or violence against women): **Bulgaria, Finland.**

Figure 1. Overview of the Comprehensiveness of the Instruments in Place (N=18)

A key message is that general legal frameworks (e.g., anti-discrimination, labour law, violence against women, or sexual harassment) are widespread and embedded in EU legislation, but do not automatically translate into policies and actions relevant to R&I and higher education, particularly where students are not covered by labour-based provisions and where institutional responsibilities, procedures, and reporting expectations are not specified for the sector.

INCREASING POLICY ATTENTION

Visible progress has occurred since 2023, with policy layering rather than single-instrument solutions.

Policy attention has increased in recent years, with a significant number of **new instruments and their revisions adopted from 2023 onwards**. This is most visible in countries that have adopted dedicated instruments or expanded sectoral initiatives.

New developments include:

- **Belgium (Flemish):** adoption of a **Decree on Transgressive Behaviour in Higher Education (2023)** and related instruments (including a 2023 circular for prevention and combating harassment, discrimination, and sexual violence in higher education contexts).
- **The Netherlands:** a sustained sequence of measures (**Integral Policy on Social Safety (2023)**, a **Programme (2024–2027)**, and associated instruments including a **Subsidy Scheme (2025–2027)** and a sectoral conference) indicating structured institutionalisation through a multi-year policy approach.
- **Portugal:** adoption of **Law n. 61/2023** addressing harassment and sexual violence in higher education.

Overall, this pattern suggests that progress is currently being made largely through **policy layering and policy mixes**, although a single framework law model is also in evidence.

ALIGNMENT WITH THE ZERO-TOLERANCE CODE OF CONDUCT

Action is more developed than Commitment, while Accountability remains the most systematic gap.

Alignment with the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct varies markedly across the three pillars: The comprehensiveness of the Action measures is more evenly spread across countries whereas Accountability shows strong divergence between countries with comprehensive mechanisms and those with emerging or absent ones; Commitment is the weakest pillar overall, with no country with comprehensive or developing framework.

Commitment: no country reaches “comprehensive” or “developing” stage

The Commitment pillar assesses whether national frameworks recognise gender-based violence as systemic and gendered, grounded in the recognition of unequal power relations and intersecting inequalities, and whether they articulate zero-tolerance principles as defined in the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct and priority groups. Under the current operationalisation, **no country reaches the “comprehensive” or “developing” commitment categories.**

- **Intermediary commitment** is recorded for eight countries: **Austria, Czechia, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal, Sweden, Norway.**
- **Absent commitment** is recorded for four countries: **Belgium, Denmark, Lithuania, Poland.**

This finding does not imply a complete lack of national commitment; rather, it highlights that **the explicit framing and conceptual elements emphasised by the Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct are not consistently codified** in national instruments for higher education and R&I. In some countries, they may be present in the broad laws and policies to counteract gender-based violence or violence against women but are not reflected or operationalised in the instruments focused on higher education and R&I.

Figure 2. Comprehensiveness of the Commitment Pillar (N=12)

Action: a substantial number of countries require/recommend multiple institutional actions, but none cover the full breadth

The Action pillar assesses whether national frameworks translate expectations into concrete institutional measures across the UniSAFE 7P framework:

- **No country is classified as “comprehensive”** (i.e., requiring/recommending a range across the full 7P spectrum).
- **Developing action** is recorded for five countries: **Belgium, Denmark, France, Ireland, Portugal.**
- **Intermediary action** is recorded for four countries: **Czechia, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Sweden.**
- **Absent action** is recorded for **Poland and Norway.**

The more detailed thematic breakdown of Action measures points to two additional patterns:

- **Prevention and protection are most frequently addressed**, indicating that many national frameworks address gender-based violence through requirements related to awareness raising, training, communication, and victim- and survivor-support measures.

- **Leadership capacity building is rarely addressed in the national policy frameworks.** Only **France and the Netherlands** are identified as explicitly recommending capacity building for senior and middle leadership roles, while nine countries do not address this dimension.

Figure 3. Comprehensiveness of the Action Pillar (N=12)

Accountability: The greatest divergence

The Accountability pillar assesses whether national frameworks include system-level mechanisms such as monitoring and evaluation, reporting requirements (including budgeting), leadership responsibility, and sanctions/enforcement. The monitoring reveals the strongest divergence across countries in this pillar.

- **Comprehensive accountability mechanisms** are in evidence in 4 countries: Austria, France, Ireland, Sweden
- **Developing accountability mechanisms:** 0 Countries
- **Intermediary accountability mechanisms:** 0 Countries

- **Emerging accountability mechanisms** are in evidence in 6 countries: Czechia, Denmark, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal; Norway
- **Absent accountability mechanisms** are in evidence in 2 countries: Belgium, Lithuania

Figure 4. Comprehensiveness of the Accountability Pillar (N=12)

Overall, this pattern suggests that a small number of countries have advanced to incorporate strong accountability mechanisms, including senior management accountability, national monitoring with indicators, evaluation mechanisms and sanctions for non-compliance. In contrast to these countries, accountability elements are under-developed or missing in the remaining countries.

STAKEHOLDERS AND DEFINITIONS

Dedicated instruments are associated with broader stakeholder engagement and broader definitions of misconduct.

Where countries have adopted sector-specific instruments, these tend to be characterised by:

- greater involvement of **multiple stakeholder groups** (e.g., other ministries, experts, NGOs, staff organisations/trade unions, student associations and initiatives, umbrella organisations); and
- **broader conceptualisation of the behaviours addressed**, increasingly including transgressive behaviour, abuse of power, intimidation, discrimination and related forms of harm (rather than only sexual harassment narrowly construed).

POLICY OUTLOOK IS STRENGTHENING UNEVENLY

No country reports policy weakening. While policy strengthening is reported in several countries, potential risks relate to institutional capacity, resourcing, and long-term sustainability.

A policy outlook indicator was used to capture whether countries report plans to strengthen, maintain, or weaken their current frameworks.

- **Strengthened outlook** for nine countries: **Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Czechia, France, Ireland, the Netherlands, Portugal, Albania**
- **Unchanged outlook** for eight countries: **Bulgaria, Denmark, Finland, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Iceland, Norway**
- **Weakened outlook for no country**

Importantly, the nature of “strengthening” varies:

- **Strengthened legislation and reporting expectations.** **The Netherlands** is highlighted as developing an amendment introducing a formal “duty of care for safety,” including obligations to monitor perceived safety, record incidents, and report serious incidents to the Education Inspectorate.
- **Framework renewal through structured evaluation and revision cycles.** **Ireland** is revising its 2019 framework following expert work and consultations, with implementation planned for 2026; **France** reports on the continuation of the 2021–2025 plan and preparation of a new roadmap following evaluation, indicating strengthening through review cycles.

At the same time, the comments received suggest that “no weakening” does not mean that risks of policy weakening are inherently absent. Where frameworks rely on fragmented provisions and ad hoc programme funding, vulnerabilities may emerge due to **resourcing and sustainability limitations**, or due to the absence of legal or policy anchoring of the instruments in place to stabilise policy implementation over time.

LIMITATIONS

The monitoring is based primarily on self-reported information from national authorities and does not assess implementation effectiveness or impact. Coverage is incomplete (as not all countries participated), cross-country legal/terminology differences affect comparability, the policy field is dynamic, and sub-national variation is currently only partially (Belgium) or not (Germany) captured in devolved systems.